

School of
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Increasing Science Literacy in the Post-Truth Era

Science Literacy Competence Framework

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Introduction: Why Science Literacy?

Disseminating science information on social media platforms can inform and influence public health policies and stimulate public debates on topics from artificial intelligence, climate crisis, genetically modified organisms (GMOs) to cloning technologies. However, these platforms can also be a vehicle for spreading science misinformation and even disinformation. There have been instances where inconclusive or retracted research articles became headlines: a well-known example is the reporting of the MMR vaccine as a cause of autism that has influenced the anti-vax movements which consequently led to the recent measles outbreak in Europe (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2024). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the World Health Organization (WHO) defines infodemic as “too much information including false or misleading information in digital and physical environments during a disease outbreak” that can cause harm and undermine public health responses. Marcia McNutt (2024), President of the National Academy of Sciences, calls for better understanding of the norms and values of science to rebuild public trust.

The spread of misinformation and disinformation on social media platforms is concerning when algorithms are designed to create personalised feeds (i.e. “For You Page”) and when these platforms are not held accountable for false reports or harmful information. Media literacy has been promoted to encourage the general public to “stop, think, check” before accepting and reposting information from any source. Table 1 shows some major campaigns and organisations that provide online, or hybrid resources, and training pertaining to concepts of media, digital, information, and news literacy in Ireland, the United Kingdom, and the United States. However, media literacy alone is not sufficient for tackling infodemic or science misinformation, especially when social media posts involve science information and vocabularies that can be misunderstood and misinterpreted. For instance, often times news articles or social media posts state: “a new study shows...” but the seemingly scientific claims are not necessarily accurate, true, conclusive, or trustworthy (Alberts, Hopkin, & Roberts, 2023), not to mention the public is not familiar with the scientific processes and norms. The following examples illustrate some vocabularies pertaining to scientific process and the necessity of science literacy, defined by the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2016) as “the familiarity with the enterprise and practice of science”:

Scientists in Germany claim to have cracked the cause of the rare blood clots linked to the Oxford/AstraZeneca and Johnson & Johnson coronavirus vaccines and believe the jabs could be tweaked to stop the reaction happening altogether. The delivery mechanism means the vaccines send the DNA gene sequences of the spike protein into the cell nucleus rather than the cytosol fluid found inside the cell where the virus normally produces proteins, Prof Marschalek and other scientists said in a **preprint paper** released on Wednesday. (The Irish Times, 2021)

Early results from a small clinical trial, presented February 17 at the annual meeting of the American Association for the Advancement of Science, suggest that a close relative of the weight-loss drugs Wegovy and Ozempic significantly lessened cravings for opioids in people with opioid use disorder. (Science News, 2024)

Efforts to reproduce the work showed that the enzymes do not catalyze the reactions with the activities and selectivities claimed. Careful examination of the first authors lab notebook then revealed missing contemporaneous entries and raw data for key experiments. The authors are therefore **retracting the paper**... The announcement is the latest example of the **reproducibility crisis** facing the sciences. (BBC, 2020)

Name	Mission	Details
IRELAND		
Media Literacy Ireland (MLI) - https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie Founded 2018	“an informal alliance of individuals and organisations who work together on a mainly voluntary basis to promote media literacy in Ireland”	Offers resources for both learning and teaching media literacy with an emphasis on child and teenage education.
National Adult Literacy Agency (NALA) – https://www.nala.ie Founded 1980	“to advocate for literacy as a human right and to collaborate with our partners to influence policy and practice to support the development of literacy, numeracy and digital skills.”	Provides resources and training for adult multiliteracies- some specific focus on health literacy and digital literacy. Mainly used for professional development.
UNITED KINGDOM		
Media and Information Literacy Alliance (MILA) - https://mila.org.uk Founded 2023	“to foster collaborations and education that empower everyone in the UK with the lifelong ability to reach and express discerning views about the information and media that they use, share and create.”	Conducts research and disseminates political briefings to emphasise importance of media literacy education, especially for school curriculums. Provides Media and Information Literacy Frameworks for teaching.
News Literacy Lab - https://newsliteracylab.org Founded 2021	“dedicated to empowering young people by equipping them with essential skills to navigate the news in today’s world.”	Provides a curriculum for teachers of tweens and teens, and offers free training for both individuals and teachers
UNITED STATES		
National Association of Media Literacy Education - https://namle.org Founded 1997	“aims to make media literacy highly valued and widely practiced as an essential life skill.”	Offers resources mainly in the form of research and online trainings for all ages; large focus on child media literacy and teaching parents
MediaWell - https://mediawell.ssrc.org Founded 2019	“collects and synthesizes research on how to mitigate the influence of false, misleading, or hateful narratives online, build resilient democratic institutions, and empower communities to inform themselves.”	Provides up-to-date summaries and access to media literacy research, aimed at informing scholars and the general public on current events and developments that could affect media literacy.
News Literacy Project - https://newslit.org Founded 2008	“building a national movement to advance the practice of news literacy throughout American society, creating better informed, more engaged and more empowered individuals — and ultimately a stronger democracy.”	Provides training, educational material, tips, and quizzes for teachers and the general public about news literacy education

Table 1 Major Literacy Initiatives in Ireland, United Kingdom, and United States

The necessity of science literacy is compounded by the proliferation of preprints and an increasing number of open access articles which can be read by journalists and the general public. Over 28,000 preprint articles have been uploaded on medRxiv and bioRxiv since the beginning of the COVID-19

pandemic. While these preprints are valuable for scientists and researchers, they have not been peer reviewed and are not suitable for journalistic reports or public consumption.

As social media posts and news reports about anxiety, stress, diet, weight loss, birth control, vaccinations, and so on are consumed and shared every day, from Sleepy Girl Mocktail (The New York Times, 2024), Ozempic for weight loss (The New York Times, 2022), to more serious health issues, diagnosing, understanding, and evaluating the process and evidence undergirding the reports are fundamental for informed citizenship and policymaking (Scheufele et al., 2021). Howell and Brossard (2021) state that, when it comes to science information, many are misinformed or uninformed broadly about how science works. Similarly, Osborne and Pimentel (2022) highlight the significance of science education in the face of science misinformation and disinformation that have become more easily widespread on social media platforms.

Furthermore, there is also a need for the public to discern potential commercial and political influences on scientific research (Oreskes & Conway, 2010), and the mechanisms by which false beliefs form and spread (O'Connor & Weatherall, 2019). Ma (2024a) argues that the understanding of the scientific process, in particular how knowledge is produced and published, is vital for combatting science disinformation and misinformation. Science literacy is important not only during a pandemic or a public health crisis, but in everyday encounters of science-related information in traditional and social media. Yet, although science literacy can be considered as a subsidiary of information literacy, the term is not commonly understood, and its practices are not well developed.

What is Science Literacy?

The National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2016) published the report, “Science Literacy: Concepts, Contexts, and Consequences” that signifies the importance of science literacy for the health and well-being of communities and society. The report analyses previous literature about the concept of science literacy at three different levels: the society, the community, and the individual, of which most are concerned with scientific knowledge and the attitudes and perceptions of science. Drawing the diverse threads of discussion, the report states:

More than just basic knowledge of science facts, contemporary definitions of science literacy have expanded to include understandings of scientific processes and practices, familiarity with how science and scientists work, a capacity to weigh and evaluate the products of science, and an ability to engage in civic decisions about the value of science. (p. 1)

More recently, Howell and Brossard (2021) suggest that science literacy involves understanding (1) “the norms and practices in science and scientific institutions shape what a single study stands for and what it means when a study is retracted”; (2) the existence of complex uncertainty and how science addresses uncertainty; and (3) the line between what science can answer and value-based considerations in decision-making. Similarly, Osborne and Pimentel (2022) highlight knowledge about social practices the scientific community uses to produce scientific findings, while also pointing to the necessity of basic digital media literacy at all educational levels. Pointing out the absence of discussions about the social nature of science at undergraduate level, they argue that “scientists and science educators have a fundamental responsibility to teach about the social mechanisms and practices that science has for resolving disagreement and attaining consensus” (Osborne & Pimentel, 2022, p. 248).

The current development of science literacy responds to the “civic” form of science literacy proposed by Shen (1975) to allow participation in the democratic processes of an increasingly technological society. Science literacy is less about the contents of science or scientific knowledge, but the *process*

by which scientific knowledge is produced when it comes to differentiating between misinformation and legitimate science in traditional and social media. In other words, understanding the scientific process means the ability to gauge whether a scientific claim is from a legitimate source, whether the source has the expertise to justify the claims, whether the claims are based on scientific consensus, and how the claims have dealt with uncertainty (Osborne et al., 2022; Osborne & Zucker, 2023). Drawing from recent publications, Table 2 illustrates three key areas of science literacy: (1) digital media literacy, (2) scientific norms, values, and practices, and (3) scientific publication process and their key concepts.

	Contents	Elements/Concepts
Digital media literacy	<p>Three skill areas (Howell & Brossard, 2021):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the ability to access science information, particularly in online environments (b) an understanding of how science information travels through media systems, particularly online; and (c) the ability to evaluate individual pieces of science information in media messages <p>Basic understanding of how the internet [including social media] is structured and how contents are shaped by algorithmic decision making (Osborne et al., 2022)</p>	<p>Production and dissemination of science information in traditional and social media</p> <p>Science facts vs opinions in media stories</p> <p>Algorithms Deepfake Generative AI Platform mechanisms</p>
Scientific norms, values, and practices	<p>Civic science literacy (Howell & Brossard, 2021):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The incremental production of scientific knowledge and why one single study can seldom uncover the mechanisms behind one phenomenon (b) the issues of reproducibility and replicability in science (c) the notion of uncertainty in science contexts and how it differs from uncertainty in lay contexts <p>Understanding scientific process (Alberts, Hopkin, & Roberts, 2023):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Who is providing or promoting the information? Do they have economic or political reasons to spread these views? (b) Whether the source of the information has the expertise and credentials needed to validate their assertion? 	<p>Conflict of interests Consensus Fabrication Replicability Reproducibility Scientific misconduct Uncertainty</p>
Publication process	<p>Civic science literacy (Howell & Brossard, 2021):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the processes related to scientific publishing, including peer review, retractions, and what makes a scientific journal trustworthy 	<p>Peer review Predatory publications Preprints Retraction</p>

Table 2 Three Key Areas of Science Literacy in the Age of Misinformation

Adopting the “fast and frugal” heuristic (Osborne & Pimentel, 2022), a three-step process has been developed to evaluate science information by Alberts, Hopkin & Roberts (2023): (1) evaluate the

credibility of information source, (2) assess the expertise in supporting scientific claims, and (3) estimate the level of scientific consensus (Figure 1). The three-step process requires knowledge about the scientific norms, values, and practices—science literacy—for example, what constitutes conflict of interests in scientific research, what constitutes expertise in a subject area, and how do scientists come to consensus and deal with uncertainty?

Over the decades, many descriptions of science literacy have been proposed, most of which are concerned with basic scientific knowledge (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2016). The ease of information exchange on online platforms and the dependence on social media platforms for all kinds of information (Walker & Matsa, 2021; Liedke, & Gottfried, 2022), including health and science information, have prompted new challenges to safeguard trustworthy information and trust in science and expertise, as well as to tackle false or inaccurate reports of science information. Hence, science literacy in the post-truth era emphasises on the skills and knowledge for evaluating the credibility and legitimacy of sources, involving digital media literacy and the understanding of scientific processes and practices.

Figure 1 A Three-Step Process to evaluate science information (Alberts, Hopkin & Roberts, 2023)

Science Literacy Competence Framework – A Proposal

To the best of our knowledge, there is currently no existing science literacy competence framework or similar. The draft framework was first conceptualised by the lead author’s work in scholarly communication (Ma, 2023; see also Ma, 2024a), informed by the history and philosophy of science (for example, O’Connor & Weatherall, 2019; Oreskes, 2019; Oreskes & Conway, 2010). Empirical research was conducted to explore students’ perception of science misinformation and disinformation on social media platforms and their coping mechanisms, as well as their knowledge about scientific process and common terms often reported in the mass media. A summary of findings can be found in the project report (Ma, Li & Shea, 2024). The draft science literacy competence framework is based on our project findings, as well as recent publications on science literacy and science education in the context of science misinformation and disinformation. Three areas have been identified (see Table 2): Digital media literacy, scientific norms, values, and practices, and publication process.

Digital Media Literacy

The incorporation of digital media literacy in science education has been proposed (Howell & Brossard, 2021; Osborne & Pimentel, 2022; Osborne, et al., 2022). Science literacy and digital media literacy must go hand in hand because science (mis/dis-)information is being reported in the fast changing media/information environment. In terms of knowledge and skills, the DigiComp (Digital Competence) Framework for Citizens 2.2 (Vuorikari, Kluzer & Punie, 2022) is most relevant. It covers five competency areas: Information and Digital Literacy, Communication and Collaboration, Digital Content Creation, Safety, Problem Solving. In each area knowledge, skills, and attitudes are outlined and used to determine an individual's proficiency level from foundational, intermediate, advanced, to highly specialised. This tool is also one of the few that is updated and comprehensive enough to incorporate AI and algorithm mechanisms in its skill set. The framework delineates three levels of competence in evaluating information, media, and digital content (Table 3).

	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced
Evaluating Information, Media, and Digital Content	1. perform the analysis, comparison and evaluation of the credibility and reliability of well-defined sources of data, information and digital content 2. perform the analysis, interpretation and evaluation of well defined data, information and digital content	1. carry out an evaluation of the credibility and reliability of different sources of data, information and digital content 2. carry out an evaluation of different data, information and digital content	1. create solutions to solve complex problems with many interacting factors that are related to analysing and evaluating credible and reliable sources of data, information and content in digital environments 2. propose new ideas and processes to the field

Table 3 Information, Media, and Data Literacy in DigiComp Framework 2.2

Our project findings show that undergraduate students (Gen Z) have a very good level of digital media literacy: they were highly aware of algorithmic-mediated contents, they devised strategies to curate their social media feeds, and they expressed scepticisms toward seemingly trustworthy sources, verified users, and individuals with professional titles. Hence, we suggest the following to be incorporated in curriculum and literacy programme design:

1) Enhance Understanding of Platform Mechanisms and AI: Include comprehensive discussions on platform mechanisms and GenAI to educate people on how their data is collected, used, and sold by platforms. It should emphasise the incentives behind algorithmic curation and advocate for greater transparency by social media companies. This transparency is essential for holding the tech sector accountable and ensuring users are aware of the forces that shape their online experiences. Encode Justice (2023), a youth-led organisation advocating for ethical AI use, provides a compelling example of the importance of deeper algorithmic understanding that can drive meaningful action in the real world. Furthermore, incorporating ethical AI and data privacy into media literacy curricula can foster critical thinking about technology's role in society. By drawing on resources and examples from scholarly literature such as *Race After Technology* (Benjamin, 2019), and *Algorithms of Oppression* (Noble, 2018), and initiatives like Encode Justice, educators can inspire students to engage with technology in ways that promote fairness, transparency, and accountability. This deeper understanding can empower students to make more informed choices and ethical practices in the platform society.

2) Encourage Positive Uses of Social Media: The proliferation of conspiracy theories, hate speech, and mis-/disinformation on social media contribute to a toxic online environment characterised by

cyberbullying, infodemics, and mental and physical health crises. We see a landscape where opinions often trump facts, and the loudest voices, regardless of their credibility, dominate the discourse. However, media literacy education should not treat social media and the internet as only a place of fear and mistrust. In advocating for a healthy and sustainable information environment, cases of social connection, civic engagement, and informed activism should be harnessed by media literacy educators. Social media and the internet have become a necessary facet of daily social life for most people, especially young adults. Acknowledging this importance, and tools for success, instead of writing off all content as dark and dangerous, is imperative for media literacy education.

Scientific Norms, Values and Practices

The primary aim of the project is to create a competence framework that can be incorporated in undergraduate curriculum, ensuring basic literacy about scientific norms, values, and practices, including publication process. Understanding scientific norms, values, and practices is vital for bolstering trust in science, while remaining vigilant about bogus and exaggerated claims, or inconclusive results. For instance, a study with a large sample size over a long period of time is likely more trustworthy than a selected small sample size. Readers should be alerted when a study is sponsored by institutions or organisations that have vested interests. Based on Howell and Brossard (2021; see Table 2), key terms are elaborated at three levels (Table 4 and Table 5). The concepts would be best illustrated with examples relevant to course contents.

	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced
Conflict of interests	The Office of Research Integrity (n.d.) states that a conflict of interest is said to occur “when an investigator’s relationship to an organization affects, or gives the appearance of affecting their objectivity in the conduct of scholarly or scientific research.” Government funding, corporate sponsorship and potential personal conflicts should be declared.	A conflict of interest does not in itself make research findings untrustworthy as long as a study follows proper procedures, methods, and reporting.	Undisclosed conflicts of interests such as commercially-, politically- and ideologically-driven research can produce skewed research findings and misguide public opinions and policymaking.
Reproducibility and replicability	Reproducibility is a principle that underpins the scientific method. It means that the results of a study can be verified, validated, and reproduced using the same data, experiments, or codes. Replicability means that consistent results can be obtained across studies that address the same research questions using their own set of data.	Reproducibility and replicability are processes by which research consensus can be obtained and research integrity substantiated.	Open research practices such as open data and open code support reproducibility and trust in science.

Research integrity	Research integrity is concerned with the conduct of researchers. Scientific misconduct involves fabricated data and images, fake peer review, plagiarism, ghost authorship, guest authorship, and other conduct that violates research integrity. Scientific misconduct may lead to retraction of articles (see Table 5).	Research integrity is fostered by scientific practices that support scientific consensus including peer review and support for reproducible research, as well as robust reporting mechanisms.	Research integrity can be enhanced when research assessments put less emphasis on the quantity of publications, sometimes referred to as the “publish or perish” research culture.
Scientific consensus	Scientific consensus is a collective position taken by scientists based on evidence validated by the majority of subject experts in a scientific domain.	Scientific consensus is achieved through practices including peer review and replication over time.	Scientific consensus can be challenged by new evidence. However, value-driven (commercial or political) research sometimes uses skewed evidence to cast doubts that hinder the correct course of action on issues such as deforestation and climate change.
Uncertainty	Scientists often express a degree of uncertainty because they tend to focus on what they do not know. A margin of uncertainty does not mean that the results are unreliable, but that the results fall within the predicted range.	Science is inherently uncertain. It is a basic view that fosters new discoveries and methods but it does not undercut the legitimacy and trustworthiness based on scientific consensus.	Commentators with vested interests sometimes use scientific uncertainty to cast doubts on value-driven contested issues such as vaccination.

Table 4 Key terms for understanding scientific norms, values, and practices

Publication Process

When scientific findings are reported in traditional and social media, they often refer to a study or peer-reviewed articles, and sometimes even preprints. However, many people do not know about the process of scientific publishing. First and foremost, a single study or a peer-reviewed article does not usually represent scientific consensus, not to mention preprints have not been peer reviewed, meaning their findings have not been vetted. Furthermore, peer-reviewed articles can be published by predatory journals, while articles in reputable journals can be retracted when errors are found. A basic understanding of the publication process means that readers are alert to the limitations of a single study and preprints, especially when findings are reported as headlines and sometimes click bait that can have significant impact on climate action, public and reproductive health, food and drug safety, and so on.

The terms—peer review, preprint, retraction, and trustworthy publications—are included in the science literacy competence framework to enhance knowledge about scientific publishing. The understanding of the publication process is important for distinguishing between reports of scientific consensus and potentially inconclusive or contested research findings. It should also be understood that scientific publishing itself is not without biases, errors, or flaws, which can lead to false or misguided reports on social media. The description and connotation of these terms may need to be updated and more terms will need to be added as new technologies, in particular generative AI, will have significant impact on scientific publishing in the near future (Ma, 2023; Ma, 2024b).

	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced
Peer review	Peer review is a process by which facts and claims are scrutinised and vetted by subject experts when evaluating a manuscript’s quality for publication.	Peer review process can be biased due to non-scientific reasons while understanding the central role of peer review in achieving scientific consensus.	New development of peer review such as open peer review and post-publication peer review.
Preprint	Preprints are preliminary reports or manuscripts uploaded on online platforms. Preprints have not been peer reviewed, meaning that their claims have not been vetted by subject experts and should not be reported as established information.	The primary function of preprints is to facilitate communication and exchange of information in the scientific community. Preprints are most common in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) disciplines and health sciences.	Most preprint servers do not monitor or moderate contents, while some require endorsement and registration before a manuscript can be uploaded due to increasing volume and potential “junk science.”
Retraction	Articles are retracted because errors are found post-publication. Retraction should be alerted to readers, especially when the articles have been reported in news and social media posts.	Retraction is a mechanism to correct the scientific record, demonstrating a process that yields scientific consensus.	Retracted articles can be due to honest mistakes, or when scientists cannot replicate or reproduce the results. Retraction can also be due to scientific misconduct and fraudulent research.
Trustworthy publications	Trustworthy publications are edited and peer reviewed by subject experts to ensure the quality of articles.	Trustworthy publications can be determined by factors such as track record, reputation, and inclusion in indexing services.	Predatory publications are not trustworthy because they do not have a rigorous peer review process and tend to prioritise income by submission or article-processing charges (APCs) than quality of articles.

Table 5 Key terms for understanding publication process

Conclusion

Science literacy is essential in the post-truth era when the accuracy and legitimacy of information becomes ever more difficult to determine. The rise of politicised information and conspiracy theories make things more complicated (Abhari & Horvát, 2024), and can ultimately cause serious damage to the scientific enterprise and trust in science and expertise. Holden Thorp (2024), the editor-in-chief of *Science*, has recently called for the teaching of philosophy of science. Scientific practices are not without flaws and the scientific community is not without bad actors. In the past few years, there have been increasing reports of misconduct, fabricated data and images, and retraction. There have also been alarming calls about publication bias and “junk science” (Ioannidis, 2005; Michaels & Monforton, 2005; Nissen et al., 2016). With the increasing use of Generative AI, “fake” articles (i.e. articles produced by Generative AI) can become difficult to detect and distinguish. A gigantic rat penis made headlines (Pearson, 2024) and went viral on social media in early 2024. Who knows what may have sailed through the peer review process, considering the example of Sokal’s Hoax (Ma, 2024b; Sokal, 2000a, 2000b). However, these issues do not mean that scientific knowledge as a whole is not trustworthy. Increased science literacy of the general public can reinforce the norms and values, and call attention to the significance of research integrity and bolster trust in science and expertise. Currently, the norms, values, and practices of scientific knowledge making are not explicitly taught; consequently, students and the general public encounter vocabularies they may not fully understand that can lead to the spread of science misinformation and disinformation. The Science Literacy Competence Framework developed in this project can be adapted, corrected, and revised for incorporation in curriculum design and literacy programmes to enhance the public understanding of science in the post-truth era.

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